

Synthesis and Pharmacological Evaluation of some New Substituted-1,8-naphthyridines and Substituted-quinazolin-4-ones as Hypotensive and CNS Active Agents

KANCHAN AGARWAL*

Department of Chemistry, Lucknow University, Lucknow-226 007

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p-(3-Aroyl-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)methoxyacetylhydrazine on reaction with isatin converted into 5 and with 2-(3'-nitro-4'-chlorophenyl)quinazolin-4-one converted into 10. Both 5 and 10 on Mannich reaction gave the desired products (7a-j and 11a-f). The compounds were evaluated for central nervous system (CNS) and hypotensive activity.

ISATIN¹, quinazolones², benzothiazoles^{3,4} and basic amides⁵ have been reported to be pharmacodynamically versatile compounds for CNS depressant activity. The present communication describes the synthesis of isatin derivatives by incorporating heterocyclic amines in the hope that product may have higher CNS activity.

Condensation of 2-aminonicotinaldehyde with substituted benzoyl acetophenone in the presence of glacial acetic acid containing a trace of concentrated sulphuric acid resulted in the formation of 3-*p*-hydroxybenzoyl-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine (1) which on treatment with ethyl chloroacetate gave ethyl *p*-(2-phenyl-3-aroyle)methoxyacetate (2). Reaction of 2 with hydrazine hydrate in methanol yielded *p*-(2-phenyl-3-aroyle)methoxyacetylhydrazine (3). The latter (3) when boiled with salicylaldehyde in ethanolic acetic acid, furnished *N*-[(2'-hydroxybenzylidene)-*p*-(2-phenyl-3-aroyle)-1,8-naphthyridinyl]methoxyacetylhydrazine (4). Isatin⁶ and *N*-methylisatin⁷ on condensation with 3 in methanol-acetic acid gave 3'-[*p*-(2-phenyl-3-aroyle)-1,8-naphthyridinyl]methoxyacetylhydrazono]-2'-indolinone (5) and its 1-methyl analog (6). The hydrazone (5) on further reaction with formalin and substituted secondary amine/aniline yielded 3'-[*p*-(2-phenyl-3-aroyle)-1,8-naphthyridinyl]methoxyacetylhydrazono]-1'-(substituted-amino/anilino)methyl-2'-indolinones (7a-j).

Acetantranils⁸ on reaction with 3 yielded 3'-[*p*-(2-phenyl-3-aroyle)-1,8-naphthyridinyl]methoxyacetylhydrazono]-quinazoline(3*H*)-4-one (8) which on treatment with benzaldehyde in acetic acid furnished 3'-[*p*-(2-phenyl-3-aroyle)-1,8-naphthyridinyl]-2'-styryl-4-(3*H*)-quinazolin-4-ones (9). The 2-(3-nitro-4'-chlorophenyl)-3,1-benzoxazine-4-one⁹ on reaction with 3 gave 3'-[*p*-3-aroyle)-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl]methoxyacetylhydrazono]-2-(3'-nitro-4'-chlorophenyl)quinazolin-4-one (10) which on reaction with substituted secondary amine in presence of formalin

gave 3'-[*p*-(3-aroyle)-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl]methoxyacetylhydrazono]-2-(3'-nitro-4'-substituted-secondary-aminophenyl)quinazolin-4-ones (11a-f). All the compounds gave satisfactory elemental analysis. Further support for their structures was obtained from their ir and in some cases by pmr and/or mass spectral data.

CNS activity: Eleven compounds were tested for their CNS activity in albino mice of either sex. Their ALD₅₀ values were determined by the method of Horn⁹. All the compounds were found to be non-toxic (ALD₅₀ > 1000 mg/kg ip). Compounds 7e, 7f and 9 induced writhing. The compounds raised the body temperature to various extents (0.2-0.8° for 7a, b, e, f, i and 9, 11c, e). In case of 7g and 7j the temperature decreased by 1.2°.

Hypotensive activity: The effects of the compounds 7a-j and 11a-f were studied on resting blood pressure and pressor responses evoked either by carotid occlusion (CO) for 15 or 30 s or by intravenous injection of noradrenaline (NA; 1-2 µg/kg) in chloralose (80 mg/kg i.v.) anaesthetised cats. The tests were carried out at a dose of 1 mg/kg intravenously.

Among the compounds screened 7b, h, e, and 11d exhibited transient fall in blood pressure by 10 (delayed), 50 (immediate) and 60 (immediate) mm Hg, respectively, which lasted for less than 10 min. On the contrary, compounds 7h and 11c, f induced transient increase in blood pressure by 80 (immediate) and 30 (immediate) mm/Hg, respectively. Furthermore, no significant effect on evoked pressure responses (CO and NA) could be observed with any of the compounds tested.

Antimicrobial activity: Compounds 7a-e and 11a-f were tested for their antimicrobial activity against several bacteria, such as *Streptococcus faecalis*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and *Staphylococcus*

* Present address: Central Institute of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants, R. S. M. Nagar, Lucknow-226 016.

aureus. The compounds **7a, b, c, d** and **11b, c** exhibited good activity.

Experimental

All the melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 177 spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A-64 spectrometer (60Hz) and EIMS on a RMU-6E spectrometer at 70 eV.

2-Phenyl-3-p-hydroxybenzoyl-1,8-naphthyridine (1): It was prepared by the method reported in literature¹⁰.

Ethyl p-(3-benzoyl-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)-methoxyacetate (2): A mixture of 2-phenyl-3-p-hydroxybenzoyl-1,8-naphthyridine (3.26 g, 0.01 mol), redistilled ethyl chloroacetate (1.22 g, 0.01 mol) and anhydrous K₂CO₃ (2.07 g, 0.15 mol) in dry acetone (20 ml) was refluxed for 18 h, then poured in cold water and the resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol, (65%), m.p. 144° (Found : C, 72.82; H, 4.88; N, 6.80; O, 15.54. C₂₈H₂₁N₃O₄ requires : C, 72.81; H, 4.85; N, 6.79; O, 15.5%) ; ν_{max} 1 730 (C=O), 1 610 (C=N) and 3 250 cm⁻¹ (NH, NH₂).

p-(3-Benzoyl-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)methoxyacetylhydrazine (3): A mixture of **2** (4.12 g, 0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (1 ml, 0.02 mol) in methanol (20 ml) was refluxed for 6–8 h and then

cooled. The separated solid was recrystallised from DMF, (60%), m.p. 198° (Found : C, 69.30; H, 4.56; N, 14.10; O, 12.08. C₂₃H₁₈N₄O₃ requires : C, 69.34; H, 4.52; N, 14.87; O, 12.06%) ; ν_{max} 1 670 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N) and 3 210 cm⁻¹ (NH, NH₂) ; m/z 398 (M⁺), 366, 338, 309, 232, 204, 127, 113 and 105.

N-[(2'-Hydroxybenzylidene)-p-(2-phenyl-3-aryloyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)]methoxyacetylhydrazine (4): A mixture of **3** (3.98 g, 0.01 mol) and salicylaldehyde (1.23 g, 0.01 mol) in ethanol (20 ml) containing a few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 12 h. The solid thus separated on cooling was recrystallised from DMF, (65%), m.p. 188° (Found : C, 71.75; H, 4.40; N, 11.12; O, 12.75. C₃₀H₂₂N₄O₄ requires : C, 71.71; H, 4.38; N, 11.15; O, 12.74%) ; ν_{max} 3 245–3 504 br (NH, OH), 1 670 (amide C=O) and 1 625 cm⁻¹ (C=N) ; m/z 502 (M⁺), 484, 408, 394, 380, 364, 336, 307, 230, 202, 125 and 113.

3'-[p-(2-Phenyl-3-benzoyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)-methoxyacetylhydrazono]-2'-indolinone (5 and 6): A mixture of isatin (1.47 g, 0.01 mol) and **3** (3.98 g, 0.01 mol) in methanol (20 ml) containing 2–3 drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 4 h, then cooled and the separated solid was recrystallised from acetic acid, (68%), m.p. 232° (Found : C, 70.48; H, 4.18; N, 13.22; O, 12.15. C₁₃H₂₂N₆O₄ requires : C, 70.45; H, 4.16; N, 13.25; O, 12.12%) ; ν_{max} 3 200 (NH), 1 705 (ring C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N) ; m/z 527 (M⁺), 311, 206, 177, 149, 117, 111 and 91.

3'-[p-(2-Phenyl-3-benzoyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)-methoxyacetylhydrazono]-1'-methyl-2'-indolinone (6): It was prepared in a similar manner from *N*-methyl isatin and recrystallised from acetic acid, (60%), m.p. 185–86° (Found : C, 70.86; H, 4.40; N, 12.90; O, 11.82. C₃₃H₂₄N₆O₄ requires : C, 70.84; H, 4.42; N, 12.91; O, 11.80%) ; ν_{max} 3 210 (NH), 1 700 (ring C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=N, N-CH₃) ; m/z 541 (M⁺), 325, 220, 191, 163, 131, 115, 100 and 84.

3'-[p-(2-Phenyl-3-benzoyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)-methoxyacetylhydrazono]-1'-piperidinomethyl-2'-indolinone (7a): To a solution of **5** (2.63 g, 0.005 mol) in DMF (10 ml) were added formalin (0.05 ml, 37%) and piperidine (0.5 ml, 0.005 mol). The mixture was stirred vigorously, then gently heated with stirring on a water-bath for 10 min and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature. The solid thus obtained was recrystallised from chloroform-hexane (b.p. 60–80°), (60%), m.p. 170–72° (Found : C, 71.18; H, 5.15; N, 13.44; O, 10.28. C₃₇H₃₂N₆O₄ requires : C, 71.15; H, 5.12; N, 13.46; O, 10.25) ; ν_{max} 3 250 (NH), 2 900 (CH₂), 1 710 (C=O) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N) ; m/z 624 (M⁺), 408, 303, 274, 246, 214 and 208 ; δ 1.41 (12H, s, 2×CH₂CH₂CH₂), 2.56 (8H, s, 2×CH₂-N-CH₂), 4.96 (4H, s, 2×N-CH₂-N), 7.33 (1H, s, H-4) and 7.93–8.1 (2H, m, H-5 and H-7).

Similarly other indolinones (**7b–j**) were prepared: **7b** (R=morpholinomethyl), C₃₆H₃₀N₆O₆, m.p. 185°;

7c (R = pyrrolidinomethyl), $C_{36}H_{30}N_6O_4$, m.p. 192°; 7d (R = *p*-chlorophenylpiperazinomethyl), $C_{42}H_{34}N_7O_4Cl$, m.p. 168°; 7e (R = *p*-methylphenylpiperazinomethyl), $C_{43}H_{37}N_7O_4$, m.p. 174°; 7f (R = *p*-methoxyphenylpiperazinomethyl), $C_{43}H_{37}N_7O_5$, m.p. 190°; 7g (R = *p*-nitrophenylpiperazinomethyl), $C_{43}H_{37}N_7O_6$, m.p. 202°; 7h (R = *N*-methylpiperazinomethyl), $C_{38}H_{33}N_7O_4$, m.p. 189°; 7i (R = *p*-chloroanilinomethyl), $C_{38}H_{27}N_6O_4Cl$, m.p. 182°; 7j (R = benzothiazolylphenylaminomethyl), $C_{45}H_{31}N_7S$, m.p. 204°.

3'-[*p*-(2-Phenyl-3-benzoyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)]-2'-methyl-4-(3H)-quinazolinone (8): Anthranilic acid (0.68 g, 0.005 mol) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (0.01 mol) for 1 h, then excess acetic anhydride was removed by distillation and compound 3 (3.98 g, 0.01 mol) added to it. The reaction mixture was heated first at low flame and finally at full flame for 2 min. Methanol (15 ml) was then added to it and the mixture left at room temperature overnight. The resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol, (65%), m.p. 228–30° (Found: C, 70.98; H, 4.26; N, 12.96; O, 11.8%). $C_{39}H_{23}N_5O_3$ requires: C, 70.97; H, 4.25; N, 12.93; O, 11.82%; ν_{max} 1 695 and 1 700 cm^{-1} (C=O), m/z 541 (M^+), 527, 311, 206, 177 and 149.

3'-[*p*-(2-Phenyl-3-benzoyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)]-2'-styryl-4-(3H)-quinazolinone (9): A mixture of 8 (5.25 g, 0.01 mol) and benzaldehyde (0.53 g, 0.01 mol) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from acetic acid, (55%), m.p. 268–270° (Found: C, 74.38; H, 4.26; N, 11.14; O, 10.16). $C_{39}H_{27}N_5O_3$ requires: C, 74.40; H, 4.29; N, 11.12; O, 10.17%; m/z 629 (M^+), 413, 308, 279, 251, 219, 203, 119 and 51.

2-Substituted-3,1-benzoxazin-4-ones (10): The compounds were prepared by reacting substituted anthranilic acid with different acid chlorides and then heating with 3 first at low flame and finally at full flame for 2 min. Methanol or ethanol (15 ml) was then added to it and the mixture left at room temperature overnight. The resulting solid was recrystallised from methanol or ethanol, (60%), m.p. 232° (Found: C, 65.14; H, 3.40; O, 14.08, $C_{37}H_{23}N_5O_6Cl$ requires: C, 65.10; H, 3.37; N, 12.31; O,

14.07%; ν_{max} 1 695 cm^{-1} (C=O); m/z 682 (M^+) 466, 361, 304, 272, 115, 95, 51 and 43.

2'-[(3'-Nitro-4'-N-substituted)phenyl-3'-*p*-(2-phenyl-3-benzoyl-1,8-naphthyridinyl)quinazolin-4-one (11a–f): A mixture of 10 (6.82 g, 0.01 mol) and heterocyclic amine (0.01 mol) in dry pyridine (30 ml) was refluxed for 24 h. The solvent was then removed from the reaction mixture and the resulting solid after washing with 2*N* HCl (25 ml) was dried and recrystallised from acetone or ethanol: 11b (R = 3-nitro-4-(4'-ethylpiperazinophenyl), $C_{43}H_{30}N_8O_6$, m.p. 214°; 11c (R = 3-nitro-4-(piperidinophenyl), $C_{42}H_{33}N_7O_6$, m.p. 206°; 11d (R = 3-nitro-4-(pyrrolidino)phenyl), $C_{41}H_{31}N_7O_6$, m.p. 242°; 11e (R = 3-nitro-4-(morpholino)phenyl), $C_{41}H_{31}N_7O_7$, m.p. 256°; 11f (R = 3-nitro-4-(homopiperidino)phenyl), $C_{43}H_{35}N_7O_6$, m.p. 218°.

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